

The construction of the Myth of Joan of Arc and its perpetuation

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Abstract

Joan of Arc, a young woman from rural France, with no formal education or military training, managed to convince the dauphin, Charles VII, to give her an army and led him to his coronation. Her actions, apparently guided only by her deep faith in the voices she believed she heard, led to the construction of her myth and its perpetuation long after her death. This dissertation examines the events and the propitious time that propelled her into becoming a major historical character. A retrospective approach, accepting Joan's medieval beliefs such as devoutness and obedience to her voices, explores how she influenced those who were in contact with her, and Max Weber's theory of domination is employed to analyse Joan's dominating power. The selected textual and visual art works, spanning from the sixteenth century through to today, inspired by Joan, are examined to investigate their role in contributing to the perpetuation of her myth. In the face of adversity, Joan of Arc's determination, faith and charisma allowed her to assert herself, leading her to sainthood and the emergence of an enduring myth about her. Joan's multifaceted image remains a source of inspiration for authors and visual artists as it dissolves conventional boundaries. She has also become an icon harnessed by several ideological factions and political parties.

Introduction

This dissertation delves into the journey of Joan of Arc and explores the construction of her myth that has led to her enduring fame. It aims to understand how a young uneducated country girl from the fifteenth century defied, against all odds, societal norms, and how her fame endures almost six hundred years after her death. Despite Joan's brief active lifespan, she has been the inspiration for many books, articles, documentaries and films. In order to clarify the basis behind her appropriation as an icon by various factions, political parties or ideological movements, this study will seek to examine the reasons behind such alignment. The objective is firstly to elucidate the underlying factors that propelled Joan of Arc to undertake her actions, specifically her determination to expel the English from France and to lead Charles VII to his coronation. I will follow with an analysis on how these events, at the time, contributed to the creation of a significant mystical figure. The objective of the second part is to provide an insight into why the multifaceted character of her life has been a source of inspiration for so many people across various periods of time and cultural boundaries, which has contributed to the perpetuation of her myth.

To appreciate fully the conception of such a myth, it is essential to examine it retrospectively to times so different from our own. The dissertation adopts a reflective approach based on information drawn on primary sources such as the trial records, the chroniclers' works and various contemporary scholarly publications. Through the analysis of the researched information, I have endeavoured to present a nuanced presentation of the socio-political-cultural environment, taking into account the context of Joan's era - fifteenth-century France. Additionally, to complete my analysis, my investigation further delves into the manner in which the enduring presence of Joan's mystical persona has been sustained not only through literature but also through the visual arts.

At the beginning of this dissertation, the historical background of the situation in France during the fifteenth century provides a contextual foundation. Through the tumultuous times of the One Hundred Years' War between France and England, Joan became a valued figure for the troops despite having little knowledge of the art of war. Under the influence of the voices that she claimed guided her, she developed confidence and boldness. In addition, her appearance at the king's court occurred at a fortuitous time when prophets could be accorded some credibility. Yet, despite her religious devotion and wish for peace,

Joan encouraged the French troops to fight the English.¹ Her subsequent capture and sale to the enemy precipitated what was eventually deemed an unfair trial by avaricious judges,² resulting in her becoming a martyr in the eyes of many and thereby fostering the creation of the myth of Joan of Arc.

The second part discusses the perpetuation of this myth through her cultural presence and her representation as a symbol of national unity. Shakespeare loosely used Joan's narrative for the purpose of entertaining his readership while Voltaire promulgated his vision of the Enlightenment through Joan's story. The works of Jules Michelet and Jules Quicherat brought Joan's deeds to light with their research based on primary source documents and records of the trial. Subsequently, their work inspired historical and cultural production on Joan. Above all, the apotheosis of Joan's popularity came with her canonisation in 1920, her status as a saint solidifying the perpetuation of her myth. During the course of the last two centuries Joan's mythical qualities have continued to be a multifaceted source of inspiration in many cultures.

¹ Henri Wallon, *Jeanne d'Arc* (France : Hachette et cie, 1875), Volume 1, 150.

² Jules Michelet, *Histoire de France* (Paris: Calmann-Lévy, 1855) Volume 10, 249.

Historical background

Throughout Joan's early childhood years, England and France were engaged in the Hundred Years' War. During the Battle of Agincourt in 1415, heavy casualties among the French nobility caused a loss of leadership including many high-ranking commanders.³ In addition, the capture of prominent French nobles, including the duke of Orléans, gave valuable bargaining power to the English.⁴ It facilitated their ascension to access the throne and marked the beginning of a new era of English dominance.⁵ In an effort to end the Hundred Year's War, Queen Isabeau, had persuaded her husband, Charles VI, who was suffering from mental illness, to ratify the Treaty of Troyes in 1420.⁶ The treaty guaranteed that if the English king, Henry V, married Catherine de Valois who was Charles VI's daughter, he would inherit the French throne upon the death of Charles VI and therefore be both king of France and England.⁷ Through this treaty, Catherine's older brother, Charles, who was the legitimate heir to the throne was disinherited. Henry V died in August 1422, and a few weeks later, Charles VI died in October 1422, undermining the Treaty of Troyes.⁸ As he lay on his deathbed within the confines of Vincennes Castle, Henry V designated his brother, the duke of Bedford, as the regent tasked with governing France.⁹ Henry V's son became king of both England and France, but the dauphin Charles also claimed the French throne.

On 12 October 1428, the earl of Salisbury under the order of the duke of Bedford laid siege to Orléans, the last city north of the Loire loyal to Charles VII.¹⁰ The Burgundians, allied with the English, were gaining land and power. Charles had proclaimed himself king of France on the death of his father.¹¹ However, neither the infant Henry nor youthful Charles were anointed in the cathedral of Reims following the ancient legitimising ritual of French kings.¹² Henry VI was crowned as king of England at Westminster Abbey in November 1429, and as king of France at Notre Dame in Paris in December 1431.¹³ However, the French people were

³ Claude Gauvard, *La France au Moyen Age du Ve au XVe siècle* (Paris : Presses universitaires de France, 1997), 355.

⁴ Anne Curry, *Hundred Years' War 1337-1453* (London: Fitzroy Dearborn, 2003), 67.

⁵ Frances Gies, *Joan of Arc: The Legend and the Reality* (New York: Harper & Row, 1981), 1.

⁶ François Sarindar-Fontaine, *Jeanne d'Arc, Une mission inachevée* (Paris : l'Harmattan, 2015), 59.

⁷ Pierre Duparc, "La Conclusion du traité de Troyes," *Revue Historique de Droit Français et Étranger* (1922-) 49, no. 1 (1971): 54. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/43850430>.

⁸ François Lemieux, "L'Application du traité de Troyes, 21 mai 1420 : au-delà de l'échec, dix années de tentatives et d'efforts au royaume de France" (*Ma diss., Université de Montréal, 2016*), 172. <https://doi.org/1866/19101>.

⁹ Gies, *Joan of Arc*, 18.

¹⁰ Régine Pernoud, M.-V. Clin, *Jeanne d'Arc* (Paris : Librairie Arthème Fayard, 1986), chap. IX, Apple books.

¹¹ Lemieux, "L'application," 74.

¹² Gies, *Joan of Arc*, 18.

¹³ Curry, *Hundred Years' War*, 2.

unwilling to embrace a ruler who held the title of king from their most formidable adversaries, regardless of treaties or coronation ceremonies.¹⁴ At the same time, Charles could not be crowned in Reims, as the city, located deep in Anglo-Burgundy territory, was inaccessible.¹⁵ Facing financial adversity and geopolitical turmoil, Charles found himself trapped in a complex situation. He was caught between the duke of Burgundy, who had taken control of Paris in 1418, and the ascendant English forces.¹⁶ The dauphin fled to Bourges, where he established his own court as a rival authority to that of his father's in Paris.¹⁷ Numerous regions continued to offer him their support, as the Armagnac party rallied around him.¹⁸ The dauphin received support from the Scottish forces, although significant setbacks befell their cause with defeats at Cravant in 1423 and in Verneuil in 1424.¹⁹ The latter paved the way for an English offensive into Maine, which succumbed to their control.²⁰ This advancement extended to the Loire region, culminating in the siege of Orléans laid in October 1428.²¹ This city held significant strategic importance due to its control over the principal bridge over the Loire River.²² Notably, Orléans assumed a pivotal role as the figurative gateway to the invading forces, hence underscoring the English's keen interest in capturing it.²³ In such a difficult situation, the kingdom could only wait for divine intervention.

Joan's voices

The voices that Joan allegedly first heard at the age of thirteen are the foundation of her mystical character. In February 1429, Joan embarked on a mission to meet the dauphin in Chinon. She claimed to be guided by divine voices, which she said asked her to expel the English from France. Joan's birthplace, the village of Domrémy, straddles the borders of Champagne and Barrois; although the English never infiltrated this area, it suffered greatly due to the kingdom's troubles.²⁴ Its inhabitants remembered better times under Louis of Orléans, when he held a protectorate over nearby territories before civil war struck.²⁵ The

¹⁴ Gies, *Joan of Arc*, 18.

¹⁵ Gies, *Joan of Arc*, 18.

¹⁶ Gies, *Joan of Arc*, 18.

¹⁷ Gies, *Joan of Arc*, 18.

¹⁸ Curry, *Hundred Years' War*, 69.

¹⁹ Curry, *Hundred Years' War*, 69.

²⁰ Curry, *Hundred Years' War*, 69.

²¹ Curry, *Hundred Years' War*, 69.

²² Régine Pernoud, *Joan of Arc by herself and her witnesses*, trans. Edward Hyams (Lanham: Scarborough House, 1994), 7.

²³ Pernoud, 7.

²⁴ Pernoud and Clin, *Jeanne d'Arc*, Chap. III, Vaucouleurs, une « anomalie ».

²⁵ Edouard Perroy, *The Hundred Years War*, (London: Eyre & Spottiswoode, 1962), 282

region shifted allegiances through the Orleanist and Armagnac periods.²⁶ From 1419, conflict raged between Charles's troops and the Burgundians, both laying waste to the countryside.²⁷ In 1428, the duke of Bedford, sought to defeat resistance in this region,²⁸ and Antoine de Vergy, the Burgundian governor of Champagne, led an incursion that displaced the defenceless peasants.²⁹ The peasants of Domrémy abandoned their homes and sought refuge within the walls of Neufchâteau, the only nearby fortified town where from the top of the ramparts, they watched their burning harvest in the distance.³⁰ Amidst the chaos, the town of Vaucouleurs, led by Robert de Baudricourt, stood firm, negotiating a temporary truce.³¹ The impact of these events on Joan whilst she was still a teenager would have been traumatising.

The surviving official Latin version of the recording of Joan's trial reveals that during her questioning, Joan said that she heard a voice for the first time on a summer's day, while in her father's garden at around midday.³² The voice came from the right side of the church. Initially frightened, Joan became used to it and said that it seemed to her that it was the voice of an angel.³³ She later explained that Saint Michael was the first apparition that she saw and that he was accompanied by angels from the sky.³⁴ When the judges and assessors asked Joan if it was the voice of an angel speaking to her, or if it was the voice of a saint, or that of God directly, she answered that these voices were those of Saint Katherine of Alexandria and of Saint Margaret of Antioch.³⁵ She added that the apparitions wore beautiful crowns, very rich and very precious.³⁶ These two saints were well-known and revered in the fifteenth century. St Margaret of Antioch was one of the most famous female saints of both the Catholic world and eastern Christianity.³⁷ Her statue, in front of which Joan probably prayed, still exists in the church of Domrémy. In addition, the cult of St Katherine of Alexandria experienced a high

²⁶ Perroy, *The Hundred Years War*, 282.

²⁷ Perroy, *The Hundred Years War*, 282.

²⁸ Pernoud and Clin, *Jeanne d'Arc*, Chap. III, Vaucouleurs, une « anomalie ».

²⁹ Perroy, *The Hundred Years War*, 282.

³⁰ Pernoud and Clin, *Jeanne d'Arc*, Chap. III, Vaucouleurs, une « anomalie ».

³¹ Pernoud and Clin, *Jeanne d'Arc*, Chap. III, Vaucouleurs, une « anomalie ».

³² Procès de condamnation, Seconde séance publique – jeudi 22 février 1431, Stejeannedarc.net, April 2023, http://www.stejeannedarc.net/condamnation/proces_index.php.

³³ Procès de condamnation, Seconde séance publique.

³⁴ Procès de condamnation, Quatrième séance publique.

³⁵ Procès de condamnation, Quatrième séance publique.

³⁶ Procès de condamnation, Quatrième séance publique.

³⁷ Juliana Dresvina, A Maid with a Dragon: The Cult of St Margaret of Antioch in Medieval England, British Academy Postdoctoral Fellowship Monographs (London, 2016; online edn, British Academy Scholarship Online, 19 Jan. 2017), <https://doi.org/10.5871/bacad/9780197265963.001.0001>, accessed 26 June 2023.

level of popularity throughout the fourteenth and fifteenth centuries.³⁸ Joan would have learned about her, as she was the patron of the church of Maxey near Domrémy.³⁹ Questioned on what the voice told her, Joan replied later that it told her to behave well, to go to church, and that it was necessary that she should go to France.⁴⁰ Later, she claimed, the voice said to her that she could no longer stay where she was,⁴¹ and when the English besieged Orléans in October 1428, it told her to raise the siege of Orléans.⁴² Despite considering herself a “pauvre fille qui ne savait monter à cheval ni conduire la guerre”,⁴³ she decided to go to the dauphin in Chinon and to engage in military conflict. Her resolution was founded upon her claimed divine revelation, wherein her voices had counselled her to take up arms. Indeed, Joan was seemingly beholden to the authority of these saints and as they appeared more frequently to her, their influence grew and became the driving force of her actions.

Whilst the role of Joan’s voices in her life decisions cannot be understated, it is essential to acknowledge the pivotal influence of medieval theology on her perception of these auditory and visual phenomena. St Thomas of Aquinas contributed to the debate on the act of faith and its reasonableness. For this influential thirteenth-century Catholic philosopher, God was the source of both faith and reason in line with the teachings of St. Augustine on the act of believing.⁴⁴ Aquinas subscribed to the notion that belief at a “natural level” entails “think[ing] with assent.”⁴⁵ This means it is a perfectly reasonable thing to accept something as true on the words of others, even in the absence of personal observation or experience. An example of this is our belief in the existence of a city we have never visited based upon the testimony of others. In a similar vein, Aquinas argued that the supernatural act of faith is a reasonable undertaking. He posited that believing information coming from a trustworthy source without empirical proof was a rational act.⁴⁶ The bishop of Avranches, who was unfavourable to Joan's trial, said that according to the doctrines of Saint Thomas, there was nothing impossible in what Joan asserted, nothing that should be rejected lightly.⁴⁷

³⁸ Katherine Lewis, *The Cult of St Katherine of Alexandria in Late Medieval England* (Boydelle and Brewer, 2000), abstract.

³⁹Anatole France, *La vie de Jeanne d'Arc*, (Library of Alexandria), 72.

⁴⁰ Procès de condamnation, Seconde séance publique.

⁴¹ Procès de condamnation, Seconde séance publique.

⁴² Procès de condamnation, Seconde séance publique.

⁴³ Procès de condamnation, Seconde séance publique.

⁴⁴ Dominic Legge “Reasonable belief: The contribution of Aquinas and his Dominican followers on the Act of Faith and its reasonableness,” *Angelicum*, vol. 93, iss. 2, (2016): 317.

⁴⁵ Legge, “Reasonable belief,” 318.

⁴⁶ Legge, “Reasonable belief,” 318.

⁴⁷ Michelet, *Histoire de France* 251.

In light of these prevailing beliefs, Joan's claim to have heard voices and seen apparitions is more plausible from a medieval person's point of view than a similar assertion in the present day.

The judges and assessors of Joan's trial recognised that God spoke through His saints. Yet, they reserved for themselves the power of deciding what the truth was. When a group of prosecutors asked her what sign she could give to indicate that her voices came from God, she responded, "Je vous l'ai assez dit que ce sont saintes Katherine et Margaret; et croyez-moi si vous le voulez!"⁴⁸ At the beginning of the trial, she said that she would tell the truth, but that she would keep secret the revelations from the saints,⁴⁹ possibly because she did not have the means to prove that the voices, the apparitions, or even that God, existed. Joan's words created a conflict with the authoritarian character of the religious representatives, but not with the Catholic religion itself because she believed she was God's messenger and she felt no obligation to prove it to anyone, including her judges. Such an unwavering faith is coherent with the medieval mind, which was often shaped by the influence of the Catholic Church. Besides, rejecting Joan's purported divine revelations would have undermined the Church's fundamental demand for unconditional faith in God. Despite the many posited explanations for Joan's hearing of saints' voices, they were emblematic of the mystical tendencies of the medieval era and constituted the underlying motivation for her accomplishments.

While the demands of Joan's voices heavily influenced her to embark on a mission to save king and kingdom, they conflicted with her earthly paternal authority urging her to remain modest and engage in labour.⁵⁰ According to Jules Michelet, Joan's decision to leave her home, family and friends can be considered as her first fight.⁵¹ Joan's father swore that if his daughter went away with soldiers, he would rather drown her with his own hands.⁵² Joan's nonconformity to the societal conventions of her time resulted from the powerful influence of the voices she heard. She persuaded her uncle to request support from Robert de Baudricourt, captain of Vaucouleurs, who received him rather coldly, and told him that there

⁴⁸ Procès de condamnation, Quatrième séance publique.

⁴⁹ Procès de condamnation, Première séance publique.

⁵⁰ Michelet, *Histoire de France*, 176.

⁵¹ Michelet, *Histoire de France*, 176.

⁵² Michelet, *Histoire de France*, 176.

was nothing to do, except to take her back to her father.⁵³ Joan refused to accept this: she had herself accompanied to Baudricourt again, and told him firmly "qu'elle venait vers lui de la part de son Seigneur, pour qu'il mandât au Dauphin de se bien maintenir, et qu'il n'assignât point de bataille à ses ennemis."⁵⁴ She believed that God would help the dauphin by mid-Lent and wanted him to become king.⁵⁵ She added that in spite of the dauphin's enemies, she would lead him to be crowned.⁵⁶ Baudricourt eventually gave Joan his authorisation on February 23, 1429.⁵⁷ Her departure from her village and family marked a pivotal moment, as it is from this point forward that her apparent ability to exercise power over those around her became evident.⁵⁸ Two men-at-arms had offered to accompany her and had taken on themselves the expenses of the trip.⁵⁹ The duke of Lorraine gave her a horse and wished her well.⁶⁰ The young men who travelled with Joan "affirmed that they never had the thought of evil with her; they were as if inflamed with the divine love which was in her soul, and became chaste and pure by the contagion of holiness."⁶¹ Even prior to her accomplishments, Joan appeared to possess an inherent mystical and charismatic ability.

Spiritual elevation

Joan's purported direct reception of divine messages through God's saints elevated her spiritual standing while diminishing the intermediary role traditionally held by the clergy as intermediaries between God and humanity. This elevation was of such magnitude that it could be perceived as placing Joan closer to God than the clergymen. During her trial, she said to her judges, "J'ai plus grande crainte de leur manquer en disant quelque chose qui déplaît à ces voix, que je n'en ai de vous répondre."⁶² In Joan's mind, only God was the instrument of her actions. She continued by saying to the assessing bishop, "Vous dites que vous êtes mon juge. Prenez garde à ce que vous faites, parce qu'en vérité je suis envoyée de Dieu, et vous mettez en grand danger."⁶³ Joan's judges launched personal attacks against her, yet in her mind, their condemnations were not directed at her but rather at God Himself, and

⁵³ Michelet, *Histoire de France*, 176.

⁵⁴ Michelet, *Histoire de France*, 178.

⁵⁵ Michelet, *Histoire de France*, 178.

⁵⁶ Michelet, *Histoire de France*, 178.

⁵⁷ Sarindar-Fontaine, *Jeanne d'Arc*, 273.

⁵⁸ Michelet, *Histoire de France*, 176.

⁵⁹ Wallon, *Jeanne d'Arc*, Volume 1, 97.

⁶⁰ Wallon, *Jeanne d'Arc*, Volume 1, 98.

⁶¹ Wallon, *Jeanne d'Arc*, Volume 1, 105.

⁶² Pernoud and Clin, *Jeanne d'Arc*, Chap. VII, Si la voix me l'a défendu.

⁶³ Procès de condamnation, troisième séance publique.

subsequently she warned them as she thought they were putting themselves at risk of displeasing God. Joan's answers to the assessors' questions confirmed a profound disconnect between herself and the representatives of the Church. Her persecutor, Pierre Cauchon, the bishop of Beauvais, and the University of Paris had hoped to continue to govern Christianity as it had done in the time of the popes of Avignon and to govern it by way of a parliamentary assembly.⁶⁴ Joan's case had disrupted their carefully laid plans.

Joan's knowledge, apparently directly obtained from God's messengers, had convinced the dauphin. Indeed, according to Jean Pasquerel, the chaplain who was Joan's confessor, after his first meeting with Joan, the dauphin said that she had told him "a certain secret that nobody knew or could know but God. That is why he had great confidence in her".⁶⁵ Joan's ability to influence the dauphin through her purported personal connection with God played a role in contributing to elevate her as a main figure of her time. Although Joan's situation may seem enigmatic when examined through the lens of today's discourse, adopting a retrospective approach is crucial in appreciating the factors that isolated her and instilled in her a sense of superiority, much to the dislike of her judges.

Prophecies

The dauphin had been previously approached by several prophetesses before Joan, women akin to her in being of humble, unmarried backgrounds and without formal education, who travelled hundreds of kilometres to disclose their prophecies to him.⁶⁶ Notably, medieval oral tradition favoured the circulation of prophetic rumours that blended the supernatural with the real.⁶⁷ These predictions, often obscure and malleable, constituted a political language capable of adapting to diverse political circumstances.⁶⁸ Some women, such as Jeanne-Marie de Maillé (died in 1414) or Péronne la Bretonne (burned in 1414), tried to gain access to the dauphin to convey God's message and convince him of his mission.⁶⁹ Prophets were questioned by members of the clergy to ensure conformity with Christian dogma.⁷⁰ If they were declared suspect of being inspired, not by God, but by the Devil, they were sent

⁶⁴ Pernoud and Clin, *Jeanne d'Arc*, chap. VII, Je ne sais sur quoi vous voulez m'interroger.

⁶⁵ Quicherat, III, p. 102-103, quoted in Gies, *Joan of Arc*, 50.

⁶⁶ Colette Beaune, *Jeanne d'Arc* (Perrin, 2004), Un ministère féminin, Apple books.

⁶⁷ Beaune, *Jeanne d'Arc*, Un ministère féminin.

⁶⁸ Catherine Daniel, "L'audience des prophéties de Merlin: entre rumeurs populaires et textes savants," *Médiévales*, 57, (2009) : 25.

⁶⁹ Gauvard, *La France au Moyen Age*, 472.

⁷⁰ Sarindar-Fontaine, *Jeanne*, 47.

immediately to the stake.⁷¹ One of the prophecies circulating in France recalled that under the reign of Charles VI, a prophetess called Marie d'Avignon had announced to the dauphin that the kingdom would pass through great calamities.⁷² She told Charles VI, "I had many visions about it. Many weapons appeared to me; I was afraid, for a moment, of being obliged to wear them myself: I was told to fear nothing, that they were not intended for me, but for a maiden who would come after me and deliver the kingdom".⁷³ Joan not only fit with the maiden in the prophecy, but also stood apart from other prophetesses; she was the only one with the intention of executing God's message herself.

Christine de Pizan, an intellectual court writer and contemporary of Joan, gives in her *Book of the City of Ladies* examples of several women, whom regardless of their religion had been granted by God the gift of prophecy.⁷⁴ Prior to Joan's encounter with the dauphin, another prophecy coming from the *Historia regum Britannia* (c. 1136) circulated regarding the arrival of a maiden who would rescue France. Joan was aware of this prophecy saying that, "France would be ruined through a woman, and afterward restored by a virgin."⁷⁵ The woman could potentially be Queen Isabeau of Bavaria, the wife of Charles VI, who had given her agreement to the Treaty of Troyes.⁷⁶ The prophecy foretold the coming of a heroine from *Bois Chesnu* who would do "admirable things."⁷⁷ During her trial the judges turned to this subject probably as a tactic that could produce evidence of Joan being implied in sorcery. Joan admitted that there was a wood half a league away from her house called Bois Chesnu, confirming that she knew of the prophecy although she said that she did not believe in it.⁷⁸ The prophecy swiftly played in her favour, assisting Joan to cement her position as a beacon of hope for the nation, and thus, contributing to her popularity.

Domination

The auspicious prophecies of the time, coupled with an undisclosed sign which Joan would refuse to reveal at her trial, contributed in convincing the dauphin of her legitimacy.⁷⁹ Joan's ability to influence those around her in the absence of any official authority can be

⁷¹ Sarindar-Fontaine, Jeanne, 47.

⁷² Fabre, *Mélanges*, 452.

⁷³ Fabre, *Mélanges*, 452.

⁷⁴ Christine de Pizan, *the Book of the City of Ladies* (London: Penguin books, 1999), 96.

⁷⁵ Gies, *Joan of Arc*, 31.

⁷⁶ Gies, *Joan of Arc*, 31.

⁷⁷ Procès, troisième séance publique.

⁷⁸ Procès, troisième séance publique.

⁷⁹ Gauvard, *La France au Moyen Age*, 472.

characterised as charismatic domination. In his reflection on domination, Max Weber, the German sociologist, distinguishes three types of domination: traditional, rational, and charismatic.⁸⁰ Traditional domination is characterised by the acceptance of a figure of authority, such as God, a king, or a lord. This type of domination is not challenged because it is based on sacred texts and traditions, which proffer authority to a person.⁸¹ Rational domination comes out of an electoral-type process where arguments are exchanged and where the candidate who seems most relevant is elected.⁸² Its legitimacy comes from respect for the law. Furthermore, there is a distinction between private life and professional life. According to Weber, the third type of domination is charismatic domination, which is represented when a person arrives, speaks and thereby triggers something particular.⁸³ Unlike traditional and rational domination, charismatic domination binds individuals to their intrinsic self.⁸⁴ In this context, an individual's authority is recognised through their mere presence and their ability to emanate power through their speech, despite the absence of a formal delegation of power. This description resonates with Joan's circumstances, for, despite her humble background, her mere presence elicited a sense of respect.

While it was traditional domination that conferred power on Charles VII through history and tradition, the perception of charismatic domination fell upon Joan. According to Weber's concept, "the recognition of those who are dominated [...] is a completely personal abandonment, full of faith, born either from enthusiasm or from necessity and hope."⁸⁵ This concept offers an insight into the reason for Joan's ability to dominate. The charisma she displayed was based on a social relationship between her and the people who believed that she was the person chosen by God to save France, thanks to the unique set of circumstances prevailing at the time. In addition, Weber writes that "no prophet has regarded his quality as depending on the opinion of the crowd towards him."⁸⁶ The English authorities saw her as a witch, while the assessors perceived her as a threat, who not only supported the dauphin, but who also directly conversed with God's messengers. Joan was subjugated by the voices she

⁸⁰ Max Weber, *Économie et Société/1 Les Catégories de la sociologie*, trans. Julien Freund, Pierre Kamnitzer, Pierre Bertrand, Éric de Dampierre, Jean Maillard, Jacques Chavy (Paris : Librairie Plon, 1971), 289.

⁸¹ Weber, *Économie et Société*, 289.

⁸² Weber, *Économie et Société*, 294.

⁸³ Weber, *Économie et Société*, 320.

⁸⁴ Weber, *Économie et Société*, 321.

⁸⁵ Weber, *Économie et Société*, 321. Translation my own.

⁸⁶ Weber, *Économie et Société*, 321. Translation my own.

purportedly heard in order to accomplish God's mission, independently of what those around her thought of her actions.

Abomination

Without submitting to biblical recommendation and despite her displayed devout and religious character, Joan took the road to Chinon donning men's clothes. When Jean de Metz spoke to Joan before her departure and asked her if she wished to travel in her own clothes, she "replied that she would rather have men's clothes."⁸⁷ The Dominican friar Martin Ladvenu reported during the rehabilitation trial that an English lord had been allowed to try to force himself on Joan whilst she was imprisoned and wearing women's clothes, but the count of Warwick, her guard, intervened in time to prevent the rape from happening.⁸⁸ Sarindar-Fontaine questions if this act was a strategy to frighten Joan, as shaken by the episode, she would have gone back to wear men's clothes for protection. However, someone must have helped her to put them back on or given her the means to do so, since the way to do that was to unshackle her feet.⁸⁹ The incident must have occurred on the night of May 26 to 27, 1431, because as the news was going round, Cauchon came to visit Joan on May 28, to observe that she had returned to wearing men's clothes.⁹⁰ Indeed, it was through this strategy, in addition to Joan's purported non-submission to ecclesiastical authority, that the prosecution gave an appearance of legitimacy to their final verdict.⁹¹

Joan's judges condemned her determination to wear men's clothes as a crime against nature, God, and the authority of the Church. Accepting gender confusion would have been unacceptable in their roles because God had a design for all things according to his will and as lawyers and churchmen, they would have sought order and submission. Cross-dressing opposed God's creation as stated in the bible: "A woman shall not wear a man's garment, nor shall a man put on a woman's cloak, for whoever does these things is an abomination to the Lord your God."⁹² The seriousness of this issue during her trial was abominable from the point of view of Joan's judges and assessors. Wearing men's clothes placed Joan in a position that transcended religious and societal norms. In spite of the ostensibly insignificant nature of this

⁸⁷ Pernoud, *Joan of Arc*, 35.

⁸⁸ Sarindar-Fontaine, *Jeanne d'Arc*, 252.

⁸⁹ Sarindar-Fontaine, *Jeanne d'Arc*, 252.

⁹⁰ Sarindar-Fontaine, *Jeanne d'Arc*, 252.

⁹¹ Pernoud, *Joan of Arc*, 179.

⁹² English Standard version bible, "Deuteronomy 22.5," <https://www.esv.org/Deuteronomy+22/>

detail to a contemporary Western person, this dissolution of conventional boundaries proved to be a pivotal factor in her trial.

Joan's rhetoric

Another feature that departed from established societal norms was Joan's language. Her rhetoric was unusual for a young uneducated girl and perturbed her assessors. When Maître Lombard, a member of the University of Paris, interrogated Joan in Poitiers during her virginity examination, he was struck by her eloquence, remarking, "Elle répondit de grande façon."⁹³ Similarly, an old lord of Vaucouleurs, commented, "Cette fille parlait très bien."⁹⁴ Additionally, Jean Barbin, a parliament lawyer, attested that Joan spoke so proficiently that the doctors who examined her perceived a divine quality in her manner of speech.⁹⁵ The judges that Joan faced during her trial were graduates and members of the faculty of the University of Paris; as such they possessed expertise in politics, legal questioning and were skilled in resolving moral dilemmas through the application of theoretical principles.⁹⁶ Nevertheless, Joan fearlessly engaged with them, rising above her social status. When asked to swear to tell the truth about what was going to be asked of her concerning matters of faith during the first trial questioning on February, 21, 1431, she defiantly replied,

au sujet de ses père et mère et sur ce qu'elle avait fait depuis qu'elle avait pris le chemin de France, volontiers en jurerait ; mais les révélations à elle faites de par Dieu, elle ne les avait dites ni révélées à personne, si ce n'est au seul Charles qu'elle dit être son roi ; ces choses-là, elle ne les révélerait, dût on lui couper la tête ; car elle les avait eues par visions ou par son conseil secret. Et dans les huit prochains jours, elle saurait bien si elle les devait révéler.⁹⁷

Joan's audacity in defying her judges sowed a threatening seed of chaos within both the ecclesiastical and legal realms. As will be shown in the second part of this dissertation, it was a behaviour, which in the future, would serve as a source of inspiration to victims of judicial or political oppression seeking justice.

Joan's distinctive rhetoric and boldness were reflected in the letters she addressed to the duke of Bedford. By summoning the English to leave France without fighting, her

⁹³ Pernoud and Clin, *Jeanne d'Arc*, Chap. II, Le Procès de Poitiers.

⁹⁴ Pernoud and Clin, *Jeanne d'Arc*, Chap. II, Le Procès de Poitiers.

⁹⁵ Pernoud and Clin, *Jeanne d'Arc*, Chap. II, Le Procès de Poitiers.

⁹⁶ "The Trial of Joan of Arc," Fordham University, translated by W.P. Barrett, [X] accessed February 20, 2023, Internet History Sourcebooks: Medieval Sourcebook (fordham.edu)

⁹⁷ Procès de condamnation, premier interrogatoire public, 21 février 1431.

correspondence conveyed a resolute message, yet it emphasised her preference towards achieving a pacific resolution. Via a letter she sent to the duke of Bedford, she implored the English to withdraw, “J’atteindrai vos gens en France, je les en ferai aller, [qu’ils le] veuillent ou non, et s’ils ne veulent obéir, je les ferai tous occire.”⁹⁸ In her correspondence, Joan desperately sought the departure of the English from France and unequivocally expressed her intent by asking them to obey her orders, threatening them to face their potential demise.

During her trial, she confessed that the narrative of the letter which she had dictated two years earlier was all hers, except for three sets of words.⁹⁹ She explained that she dictated, “rendez au roi” instead “rendez à la Pucelle.”¹⁰⁰ She also declined having said “je suis chief de guerre”, and the third set of words is “corps pour corps.”¹⁰¹ There are several possibilities to these discrepancies. Being illiterate, Joan had no means to check the wording of her letter. It is possible that she denied having dictated these words as a way of defending her case in court by trying to minimise her role,¹⁰² or perhaps someone from her party had changed the original wording of the letter. It could have been a well-meaning amanuensis who might have felt that “Pucelle” would carry greater persuasion and potency compared to mentioning “roi”, transcending the king’s status at a time when the English troops may have felt vulnerable and fearful of “la Pucelle” because they had just lost several battles including Patay. However, echoing her previous declaration, Joan declared that she did not write these letters “through pride or presumption, but by the commandment of our Lord”.¹⁰³ Joan’s letters are stamped with three elements, her profound patriotism, her devoutness towards God and her wish for a peaceful resolution. Even if there are doubts regarding the full veracity of some of the words in the letters she sent to the English, her correspondence is nevertheless seen as a testament to her commitment to noble sentiments.

Joan’s sword

Despite her professed desire for a nonviolent resolution to evict the English out of France, Joan was known for bearing a sword with her during military campaigns. The assessors

⁹⁸ Guillaume Cousinot de Montreuil, Pierre Cochon, and Auguste Vallet de Virville, *Chronique de la Pucelle.1400-1484* (France : Delahay, 1859), 282.

⁹⁹ Procès de condamnation – Cinquième interrogatoire public – March, 1, 1431.

¹⁰⁰ Procès de condamnation – Cinquième interrogatoire public – March, 1, 1431.

¹⁰¹ Procès de condamnation – Cinquième interrogatoire public – March, 1, 1431.

¹⁰² Sarindar-Fontaine, *Jeanne d’Arc*, 99.

¹⁰³ Quicherat, Procès, Vol. 1, 239.

who presided over her trial were particularly interested in the significance of this sword as it seemed to contradict her claims of divine guidance. They asked: “Aimiez-vous mieux votre étendard ou votre épée ?”, to which she responded “J’aimais mieux, voire quarante fois, mon étendard que mon épée.”¹⁰⁴ Joan held her standard in much higher regard than her sword, and would hold it in her hand instead of her sword to avoid killing anyone.¹⁰⁵ Her sword was a symbol of authority, rather than a tool for killing. She had been given a sword at Vaucouleurs by Robert de Baudricourt at the time of her departure,¹⁰⁶ but she also asked the chapel clergy of the village of St. Catherine-de-Fierbois to look for a sword that was buried behind the altar and to let her have it if they wished.¹⁰⁷ Indeed, she claimed her voices had informed her that a rusty sword with five crosses on it was buried there.¹⁰⁸ She had shown reverence by stopping to pray in this church while waiting to travel to Chinon, and the priests were eager to accommodate her request.¹⁰⁹ Once the sword had been found, both the clergy of St Catherine and the people of Tours provided her with two sheaths for it, one of crimson velvet, the other of cloth of gold as a gift of appreciation.¹¹⁰ Joan’s emblematic sword was a physical manifestation of her paradoxical mission, which sought to both end the conflict peacefully and to engage in combat when necessary.

The lifting of the siege of Orléans.

In 1428, determined to accomplish her mission, Joan accompanied Charles VII’s army to Orléans where the English besieged the stronghold of Orléans and captured Fort des Tourelles. This was a strategic location that controlled access to the southern entrance of the bridge leading into the city.¹¹¹ Subsequently, they established a network of forts encircling the city and imposing a blockade to exert their military dominance.¹¹² Joan entered Orléans fully clad in armour, bearing her sword and standard, mounted on a white horse. This had been planned in the evening in order to circumvent the tumultuous haste of a throng of admirers because by then, she had amassed a formidable reputation.¹¹³ The *Journal du siège*

¹⁰⁴ Pernoud et Clin, *Jeanne d’Arc*, chap. VII, Je sais bien que ces Anglais me feront mourir.

¹⁰⁵ Procès de condamnation, Procès d’office, quatrième interrogatoire public, February, 2, 1431.

¹⁰⁶ Procès de condamnation, Procès d’office, quatrième interrogatoire public, February, 2, 1431.

¹⁰⁷ Procès de condamnation, Seconde séance publique.

¹⁰⁸ Procès de condamnation, Seconde séance publique.

¹⁰⁹ Procès de condamnation, Seconde séance publique.

¹¹⁰ Procès de condamnation, Seconde séance publique.

¹¹¹ Pernoud et Clin, *Jeanne d’Arc*, chap.1, L’investissement.

¹¹² Pernoud et Clin, *Jeanne d’Arc*, chap.1, L’investissement.

¹¹³ Wallon, *Jeanne d’Arc*, Volume 1, 139.

(1428-1429) mentions that for the people of Orléans, “Jeanne, en effet, était pour eux comme l’ange du Dieu des armées. [...] Ils se sentaient tous réconfortés et comme de-assiégés par la vertu divine qu’on leur avait dit être dans cette simple pucelle.”¹¹⁴ Jean renewed her demand to the English on the right bank to surrender, but it was badly received.¹¹⁵ The next day, on May 2, while she went out on horseback to examine the fortifications and English positions, large crowds who had found solace in her presence and a seemingly unassailable spirit, followed her.¹¹⁶ Even when confronted with warnings of the formidable strength of the English army and the daunting prospect of triumphing over them, Joan remained resolute in her convictions, replying that there was nothing impossible in the power of God.¹¹⁷ It seemed that Joan’s conviction in the potency of divine intervention to recover the city of Orléans rendered failure an implausible outcome.

Her first success occurred during the assault of Tour de Saint-Loup, the English fortress that was heavily defended by Talbot.¹¹⁸ This site commanded the crossing of the Loire upstream and opened the way to the Burgundy region.¹¹⁹ Joan, joined by the count of Dunois, her squire, her page, a large number of nobles, and around 1,500 soldiers went to attack the *bastide* of Saint-Loup.¹²⁰ Once arrived in front of the *bastide*, Joan ordered them to observe the enemy, and to prevent others to come to their aid.¹²¹ Standing on the edge of the ditch, her standard in her hand, she encouraged her men to attack.¹²² This triumph was celebrated in Orléans as the first act of deliverance.¹²³ She subsequently pledged that within five days, the city siege would be lifted, and not a single Englishman would remain encamped before Orléans.¹²⁴ Though Joan had contributed to lead the charge to victory, she was quick to attribute it to the power of God.¹²⁵ Her words evoked a profound sense of faith among the people who flocked to the churches to celebrate the event whilst the sound of the bells

¹¹⁴ “Journal du siège,” Procès, tome IV, 151-153, quoted in Wallon, 140.

¹¹⁵ Wallon, *Jeanne d’Arc*, Volume 1, 146.

¹¹⁶ Journal du siège d’Orléans 1428-1429, published by Paul Charpentier and Charles Cuissard, (Orléans : H. Herluison, 1896) 80.

¹¹⁷ Wallon, *Jeanne d’Arc*, Volume 1, 146.

¹¹⁸ Wallon, *Jeanne d’Arc*, Volume 1, 150.

¹¹⁹ Wallon, *Jeanne d’Arc*, Volume 1, 150.

¹²⁰ Journal du siège d’Orléans 1428-1429, 81.

¹²¹ Wallon, *Jeanne d’Arc*, Volume 1, 150.

¹²² Wallon, *Jeanne d’Arc*, Volume 1, 150.

¹²³ Wallon, *Jeanne d’Arc*, Volume 1, 152.

¹²⁴ Wallon, *Jeanne d’Arc*, Volume 1, 152.

¹²⁵ Wallon, *Jeanne d’Arc*, Volume 1, 152.

resonated with their exultant mood at the sight of the vanquished English forces.¹²⁶ Joan's perceived divine qualities, her unwavering devotion to her country, and above all her devoutness to God reinforced her impression on the population.

Christine de Pizan

Joan's deeds were recognised by the general public during her time, but they also inspired many thinkers in subsequent generations. The first author to acknowledge Joan as a remarkable woman worthy of praise was Christine de Pizan, a fifteenth-century professional writer and advocate of greater equality and respect for women. She composed the *Tale of Joan of Arc* in 1429, a long poem of sixty-one verses and the first major literary work to honour her.¹²⁷ Christine's poem begins with exultation, celebrating the king's recent coronation, which was deemed an act of providence, occurring less than two weeks before the writing of poem.¹²⁸ It also celebrated the victory that resulted, according to Christine, from the extraordinary bravery of Joan who was blessed by God and foretold by prophecies.¹²⁹ In her poem, Christine thanks God and glorifies Joan's work as in verse 21 and 22:

Et toy, Pucelle beneurée,
Y dois-tu ester obliée,
Puisque dieu t'a tant honneurée,
Qui as la corde desliée,
Qui tenoit France estroit lieé.
Te pourroit-on assez louer
Quant, ceste terre humiliée
Par guerre, as fait de paix douer ?¹³⁰

Even before her death, Joan was emerging as a pivotal literary character with divine qualities worthy of note. In her capacity as a political writer engaged in contemporary issues, Christine demonstrated an awareness of the dire situation confronting France.¹³¹ Indeed, her earliest works showed an Orleanist partisan disposition alerting her readers to the danger of Burgundian aspirations to authority.¹³² Her patriotic poem, capturing a surge of optimism and triumph, conveys her gratitude for Joan's actions as she believed that Joan had finally

¹²⁶ Wallon, *Jeanne d'Arc*, Volume 1, 152.

¹²⁷ Nora M. Heimann, *Joan of Arc: her image in France and America* (Washington DC, Corcoran Gallery of Art in association with D. Giles, 2006), 28. <https://archive.org/details/joanofarcherimag0000heim/page/28/mode/2up>

¹²⁸ Nora M. Heimann, *Joan of Arc*, 28.

¹²⁹ Jules Quicherat, *Procès de condamnation et de réhabilitation de Jeanne d'Arc* (Paris : Renouard et Cie, 1841), 4-21.

¹³⁰ Quicherat, *Procès*, 9-10.

¹³¹ Tracy Adams, *Christine de Pizan and the Fight for France*, (Pennsylvania State University Press, 2014), 174.

¹³² Adams, *Christine de Pizan*, 174.

succeeded in bringing peace in France.¹³³ Despite Christine being cloistered in the monastery of Poissy for eleven years,¹³⁴ it is noteworthy that news of Joan's exploits reached her within a few days of their occurrence. They were significant enough to prompt Christine to compose a long poem about them. As her last lines and the first major work composed on Joan, the poem had a unique claim to fame; in addition, it contributed to elevate Joan to a position of distinction on the stage of history.

The trial irregularities

Joan's standing public support on the genuineness of her intentions to deliver France from its enemies and to secure the coronation of the dauphin was reinforced by the outcome of the first trial which unfolded in a climate of uncertainty without any clear initial charges against her. Joan was to stand trial in Rouen, a city sympathetic to France and located in Anglo-Burgundian territory. Cauchon, the bishop of Beauvais, had gathered an impressive jury, Joan was alone before at least 40 persecutors; no lawyer assisted her, contrary to the customs of the Inquisition.¹³⁵

The trial did not start well for the assessors; the virginity test that would have convinced them that Joan was lying demonstrated that she was telling the truth, and worked to her advantage.¹³⁶ A motive for the physical examination was to dispel suspicions that Joan was a witch.¹³⁷ It was believed that witches made a pact with Satan that involved sexual intercourse with a demon, and therefore could not be a virgin.¹³⁸ Indeed, it would have been to Cauchon's advantage to proclaim that Charles VII owed his coronation to a heretical witch.¹³⁹

Cauchon directed Joan to recite a *Pater Noster*, perhaps in the superstitious idea that, if she were doomed to the devil, she would not say this prayer.¹⁴⁰ However, an unanticipated hindrance materialised when she replied, "Hear me in confession and I will gladly tell you."¹⁴¹ Joan's request for the bishop to hear her confession was evidently incongruous with the

¹³³ Quicherat, *Procès*, 9-10.

¹³⁴ Adams, *Christine de Pizan*, 174.

¹³⁵ Pernoud and Clin, *Jeanne d'Arc*, chap. VII, Double irrégularité.

¹³⁶ Pernoud and Clin, *Jeanne d'Arc*, chap. VII, Double irrégularité.

¹³⁷ Gies, *Joan of Arc*, 55.

¹³⁸ Gies, *Joan of Arc*, 55.

¹³⁹ Pierre Tisset, *Procès de Condamnation de Jeanne D'Arc*, (Switzerland: Droz, Librairie, 1971), Tome III, 5.

¹⁴⁰ Michelet, *Histoire de France*, 239.

¹⁴¹ Pernoud and Clin, *Jeanne d'Arc*, chap. VII, Je ne sais sur quoi vous voulez m'interroger.

practices observed in an Inquisition trial.¹⁴² Joan exhibited cleverness by reminding Cauchon of his role as a priest, because as such, he was morally obligated to accord the sacrament of penance the same importance that Joan attributed to it herself.¹⁴³

Cauchon intended to conduct a heresy trial against Joan; yet during the whole trial, she was treated as a war prisoner, locked-up and guarded by soldiers.¹⁴⁴ The events of the trial unfolded amidst the ambiguity surrounding whether Joan was a suspected heretic or a captive of war, which represented an obvious flaw in the trial. Cauchon was aware that a trial for heresy would have necessitated confinement in an ecclesiastical prison where Joan would have been under the supervision of female guards and subjected to decent and relatively comfortable conditions that were consistent with the prevailing practices for women accused of heresy at the time.¹⁴⁵ The trial was a "completely exceptional phenomenon"¹⁴⁶ because it consisted solely of the interrogations of the accused without anyone knowing, to begin with, what charge had been brought against Joan.

In addition, Jean de La Fontaine, a lawyer from Rouen, who had been appointed by Cauchon to lead the interrogations harboured a guilty conscience about Joan's situation.¹⁴⁷ He felt he could not leave her without counsel and unaware of the existence of judges of appeal, and her entitlement to seek recourse through them.¹⁴⁸ Concurrently, Jean de La Fontaine and the two monks advocated for submission to the supreme authority vested in the pope and requested access to Joan's prison.¹⁴⁹ They advised her to lodge an appeal which filed to both the pope and to the council the next day.¹⁵⁰ Furious, Cauchon summoned the guards and asked them who had visited the Maid.¹⁵¹ La Fontaine and the two monks vanished, taking with them the last vestiges of legal legitimacy from the proceedings.¹⁵²

It was on May 29, when Joan, feeling threatened, had attired in men's clothing, that the judges and principal assessors convened to deliberate upon her relapse. At the start of

¹⁴² Pernoud and Clin, *Jeanne d'Arc*, chap. VII, Je ne sais sur quoi vous voulez m'interroger.

¹⁴³ Pernoud and Clin, *Jeanne d'Arc*, chap. VII, Je ne sais sur quoi vous voulez m'interroger.

¹⁴⁴ Pernoud and Clin, *Jeanne d'Arc*, chap. VII, Je ne sais sur quoi vous voulez m'interroger, Prisonnière de guerre ou prisonnière d'église ?

¹⁴⁵ Pernoud and Clin, *Jeanne d'Arc*, chap. VII, Je ne sais sur quoi vous voulez m'interroger.

¹⁴⁶ "Procès de condamnation," *tome. III*, 85, quoted in Pernoud and Clin, *Jeanne d'Arc*, chap. VII, Double irrégularité.

¹⁴⁷ Michelet, *Histoire de France*, 248.

¹⁴⁸ Michelet, *Histoire de France*, 249.

¹⁴⁹ Michelet, *Histoire de France*, 249.

¹⁵⁰ Michelet, *Histoire de France*, 249.

¹⁵¹ Michelet, *Histoire de France*, 249.

¹⁵² Michelet, *Histoire de France*, 249.

the meeting, Cauchon said that Joan had been counselled to “return into the way of truth”, and had signed an abjuration.¹⁵³ However, Joan’s trial was marred by irregularities and the prevailing sentiment among the majority of the assessors advocated for the delivery of another sermon to Joan, accompanied by a reiteration and elucidation of the abjuration.¹⁵⁴ It was posited that if she remained obstinate in her stance, the judges would be left with no alternative but to pronounce her a heretic and hand her over to secular authorities for execution by burning.¹⁵⁵ It is worth noting that their opinions were merely of an advisory nature.¹⁵⁶ Cauchon, expressing gratitude to the assessors, announced that he would proceed against Joan “as a relapsed heretic according to law and reason.”¹⁵⁷ On May 30, he dispatched two assessors to convey to Joan her impending sentence of death. In this context, Joan epitomises the quintessential political prisoner, whose persecution stems from the obstruction posed by a prevailing authority, while seeking any conceivable pretext for her condemnation.¹⁵⁸ The general consensus that the trial was unjust resulted in her transformation from a saviour of France and facilitator of the coronation of its king, into a martyr for her noble ideals of greatness and pureness.

An enduring fifteenth-century figure

Joan of Arc stands as a defining historic figure of the fifteenth century with her prominent reputation enduring for over six centuries, passed down through successive generations. Despite the changing perspectives and inconsistencies surrounding her life, a long-lasting symbol of righteousness has been associated to her person. Her simple background has enabled people from all walks of life to connect with her. Certainly, she represents the average person allowing everyone to identify with her, but she apparently experienced something extraordinary. Undoubtedly, Joan’s significance in history is largely attributable to the people around her who elevated her to a main historic figure. The clerks, such as Brother Jean Pasquerel and Eudes de Guitry who surrounded her initially to write her letters because she was illiterate; and later on, the court clerks, including Clément de Fauquembergue, were instrumental in documenting her character and the remarkable driving

¹⁵³ Gies, *Joan of Arc*, 218.

¹⁵⁴ Gies, *Joan of Arc*, 219.

¹⁵⁵ Gies, *Joan of Arc*, 219.

¹⁵⁶ Gies, *Joan of Arc*, 219.

¹⁵⁷ Quicherat, *Procès*, Vol. 1, 459-476, quoted in Gies, *Joan of Arc*, 219.

¹⁵⁸ Pernoud and Clin, *Jeanne d’Arc*, chap. VII, Je ne sais sur quoi vous voulez m’interroger.

force behind her actions even before grasping their historic importance. While it is indisputable that Joan's leadership relied on the backing of Charles VII and the army that he provided her, her entrance was opportune, coinciding with a time when the French people needed someone like her. Her belief in her mission and subsequent martyrdom further cemented her position in history.

The perpetuation of Joan's myth

The previous chapter has delved into the construction of Joan of Arc's myth by examining the events of her life and elucidating the elements that propelled her to a position of remarkable significance. The focus of this dissertation now shifts towards the perpetuation of this myth by exploring how Joan's legendary status changed and endured. Numerous texts have been written about Joan, yet this dissertation focuses on significant scholarly and literary texts, events, and art that have played a part in perpetuating the myth. These elements are presented chronologically, shedding light on both the positive and the adverse perceptions of Joan's myth over time.

Perceval de Cagny

A preeminent source of information on Joan of Arc comes from the chronicles of Perceval de Cagny, a work that started around 1436 and which was completed around 1438,¹⁵⁹ representing an early primary comprehensive account of her life. This text survives in the form of a copy, from the hand of André Duchesne, a seventeenth-century French historian, which the archivist-palaeographer, Henri Moranvillé published in 1902.¹⁶⁰ Although being among the earliest chronicles documenting Joan's life, it bears scrutiny for potential partiality due to Perceval de Cagny's loyal affiliation to the duke of Alençon. Furthermore, this account could conceivably be susceptible to imprecision since it relied upon Perceval de Cagny's recollection of events that had transpired six years earlier. In his 2015 book, *Jeanne d'Arc, une mission inachevée*, François Sarindar-Fontaine posits that Perceval de Cagny could have built his account from hearsay, primarily due to the absence of both himself and the duke of Alençon from the events in Orléans.¹⁶¹ There are proven errors in Perceval de Cagny's text;¹⁶² nonetheless while Perceval de Cagny's reliability may be inconsistent, it must be acknowledged that he speaks explicitly of the orders given by Joan to the captains at specific times.¹⁶³

¹⁵⁹ Sarindar-Fontaine, *Jeanne d'Arc*, 117.

¹⁶⁰ Sarindar-Fontaine, *Jeanne d'Arc*, 117.

¹⁶¹ Sarindar-Fontaine, *Jeanne d'Arc*, 117-118.

¹⁶² Perceval de Cagny mistakenly made Joan sleep at the Augustins at the end of the fighting there, whereas historical evidence confirms her return to town to sleep. In addition, he omits any mention of Joan's shoulder wound. (Sarindar-Fontaine, *Jeanne d'Arc*, 117-118)

¹⁶³ Sarindar-Fontaine, *Jeanne d'Arc*, 117.

Perceval de Cagny dedicated a substantial portion comprising forty pages of his chronicles to describe the time of Joan's arrival in Chinon till the end of her life. In opposition, other prominent chroniclers of the time hardly mention Joan's actions. It was the case for Charles VII's herald, Gilles le Bouvier, and for Jean Juvénal des Ursins, the bishop of Reims.¹⁶⁴ Moranvillé claims that Perceval de Cagny's chronicle offered an unbiased account of the events.¹⁶⁵ Indeed, he explained that Perceval de Cagny demonstrated fairness in his narration, thereby rendering justice to the bravery of Charles VII.¹⁶⁶ This is the case when Perceval de Cagny remarked that all the dauphin's subjects were astonished at his apathy and at the "petit vouloir" he showed to reclaim his kingdom before his departure for his coronation in Reims.¹⁶⁷ Yet, Perceval de Cagny acknowledged Charles VII's pivotal role in the successful lifting of the siege of Montereau in 1437.¹⁶⁸ Quicherat, being the first to publish Perceval de Cagny's testimonies, recognised his balanced view.¹⁶⁹ Utilising this information, Quicherat, whose subsequent book influenced several authors and artists, exemplified Perceval de Cagny's significant contribution to the construction of the myth of Joan.

Nullification trial

Joan's story persisted through the writing of Perceval de Cagny, but above all, in the memory of the people, including the clergy and the monarchy. The pope, Calixte III, in a rescript dated June 11, 1455, had granted a request and ordered a revision of Joan's trial.¹⁷⁰ Two major arguments supported the claim for a second trial: Joan had asked to submit to the pope's supreme authority and she had never disowned the king.¹⁷¹ On November 7, 1455, a huge crowd seeking reparation for Joan's trial congregated at Notre-Dame cathedral in Paris for the opening of the inquiry.¹⁷² A quarter of a century after Joan's condemnation and death, the political situation had changed significantly. The English had been expelled from France and Cauchon had died. Another image of Joan emerged from all of the testimonies. Pernoud and Clin assert, the testimonies came from people who had personally known Joan, painting

¹⁶⁴ Sarindar-Fontaine, *Jeanne d'Arc*, 117.

¹⁶⁵ Moranvillé, *Chroniques de Perceval de Cagny*, XII.

¹⁶⁶ Moranvillé, *Chroniques de Perceval de Cagny*, XII.

¹⁶⁷ Moranvillé, *Chroniques de Perceval de Cagny*, XI.

¹⁶⁸ Moranvillé, *Chroniques de Perceval de Cagny*, XII.

¹⁶⁹ Moranvillé, *Chroniques de Perceval de Cagny*, XII.

¹⁷⁰ Gies, *Joan of Arc*, 235.

¹⁷¹ Philippe Contamine, "Le procès en révision de la condamnation de Jeanne d'Arc (1450-1456) : raisons, obstacles, procédure, résultats," *Histoire de la justice* n° 30 (2020) : 19. DOI : 10.3917/rhj.030.0017

¹⁷² Gies, *Joan of Arc*, 235.

an apparently truer portrait of her.¹⁷³ Once the instruction finished and the new information had been gathered in a voluminous file, the new Archbishop of Rouen, cardinal d'Estouville, opened the second trial which aimed to clear Joan of all the charges brought against her.¹⁷⁴ On July 7, 1456, in the great hall of the archiepiscopal palace of Rouen, Jean Juvénal des Ursins, read the document that annulled the procedure of condemnation: "We say, pronounce, decree, and declare the said trial and sentence to be contaminated with fraud, calumny, wickedness, contradictions, and manifest errors of fact and law, and together with the abjuration, the execution, and all their consequences, to have been and to be null..."¹⁷⁵ A copy of the account of first trial was symbolically torn in front of the crowd.¹⁷⁶ Through the nullification trial, the honour of Joan of Arc and her family was reinstated and several ceremonies took place in Rouen and in other cities in France.¹⁷⁷

Although Charles VII had not initiated an investigation into Joan's trial, he had acquiesced to requests from the city of Rouen because he wished to know the truth about the proceedings of the first trial.¹⁷⁸ Indeed, it was not to his benefit to attribute his coronation journey to Reims to a woman who had been condemned for heresy. The outcome of the second trial served as a means of indirect redemption for Charles VII.¹⁷⁹ Moreover, although the primary objective of the nullification trial was to demonstrate the irregularities of the initial trial and to absolve Joan from the charge of heresy, it also permitted Joan's popularity to thrive in the years following her death.

Joan's cultural presence in early literature

While Joan of Arc's image remained highly favourable in France, particularly after the nullification trial, unsurprisingly, the English memory of her was less positive. This is evidenced by Shakespeare's play, *Henry VI*, where Joan's characterisation, as a divine emissary and saviour, is significantly distorted. At the time, this historical drama, written between 1588 and 1590, reflected the English theatre's enthusiasm for patriotism and historical plays. Although the play was not performed much after 1592, it saw a revival in the twentieth and twenty-first centuries. Shakespeare's depiction of Joan as a terrifying witch is

¹⁷³ Pernoud and Clin, *Jeanne d'Arc*, chap. VIII, Le vrai procès.

¹⁷⁴ Laurent, *Saint Jeanne d'Arc*, 164, 167.

¹⁷⁵ Gies, *Joan of Arc*, 236.

¹⁷⁶ Gies, *Joan of Arc*, 237.

¹⁷⁷ Pernoud and Clin, *Jeanne d'Arc*, chap. VIII, Le vrai procès.

¹⁷⁸ Laurent, *Saint Jeanne d'Arc*, 164.

¹⁷⁹ Contamine, "Le procès en révision," 17.

emphasised in these interpretations.¹⁸⁰ In a huge deviation from the now accepted historical events, Joan is portrayed a naive woman who was manipulated by the duke of Suffolk. The duke's purported intention, in order to consolidate his control over the kingdom through her, is to wed Joan to the king of England.¹⁸¹ Moreover, Talbot, who appears in the play as an English commander, accuses her of having numerous lovers. Her virtuous image and her spirituality are maligned as being demonic, while her virginity is turned into a shameful pregnancy.¹⁸² In Act 6, while she hopes to escape the pyre, she is called a "whore", and an accomplice of Satan, before leaving the stage under escort.¹⁸³ If the play reflected the persistent deviousness of the English in the treatment of Joan of Arc, it paradoxically contributed to her notoriety as a powerful woman by reappearing in the pages of English literature.

Shakespeare obviously did not want to depict Joan as virgin mythical figure, but rather as a witch and the source of triumphant evil. The playwright fails to depict Joan under the flames, the pivotal event that contributed to the creation of the French cultural narrative of sacrifice and myth surrounding her. Shakespeare's omission of Joan's passage to the stake may have been motivated by his purpose of entertaining his audience, but also by the spectators' perception of the reality of burning alive a young girl who had claimed to be God's messenger. It would have cast Joan as a martyr, and conceivably prompt them to sympathise with the tragic fate of Joan. Ironically, Shakespeare's endeavour played a role in sustaining Joan's presence in the collective consciousness of a certain public, thereby perpetuating the construction of her myth.

Although Shakespeare's portrayal of Joan of Arc was largely unfavourable, her enduring myth continued to positively inspire illustrious French writers. Among these was Jean Chapelain - one of the intellectuals who helped found the Académie Française. In 1656, he wrote a long poem called *La Pucelle, ou la France délivrée* at the behest of the duke of Longueville, a descendant of Joan of Arc's companion-at-arms, the count of Dunois.¹⁸⁴ The well-known seventeenth-century poem, loosely based on Joan's life and in part fictitious,

¹⁸⁰ Lettres Modernes, *Henry VI de William Shakespeare* (2012), 17.

¹⁸¹ Lettres Modernes, *Henry VI*, 17.

¹⁸² Lettres Modernes, *Henry VI*, 17.

¹⁸³ Lettres Modernes, *Henry VI*, 17,

¹⁸⁴ Nora M. Heimann, "Joan of Arc in French Art and Culture," in *Satire to Sanctity* (United Kingdom: Taylor & Francis, 2017), 39.

celebrated the liberation of Orléans, the restoration of the French throne, and the reunification of France.¹⁸⁵ Chapelain expressed his admiration for Joan, writing: “Je suis demeuré ferme à la Pucelle, et je l’ai constamment préférée à tant de Héros, [...] en m’attachant à cette Héroïne, dont la richesse n’aurait pas besoin de mon secours.”¹⁸⁶ Joan was the noble and illustrious protagonist of Chapelain’s poem.

Indeed, Chapelain depicted Joan’s persona in a favourable light, going so far as to refer to her as a saint, years before her canonisation, thereby elevating her status even further. He wrote :

Guerre et mort à l’Anglais !
La Sainte, contre lui, d’un saint zèle embrasée,
En jure la ruine et la promet aisée.”¹⁸⁷

Chapelain portrays Joan as encouraging the fight against the English, representing her as a warrior endowed with invincible virtuous powers. It is worth noting that in order to avoid repeating himself in his poem, Chapelain used twenty-one different ways of designating Joan, of which only four were unfavourable and placed in the mouths of the English.¹⁸⁸ The historian, Françoise Michaud-Fréjaville, completed a systematic survey of Joan’s designations in Chapelain’s poem. Joan was presented under three figures: the saint, the warrior and the girl or maiden, even “the Maid”. The designation of “saint” was particularly favoured and placed Joan’s achievements within the context of God’s divine plan.¹⁸⁹

Although the poem received severe criticism from the French literary world which prevented the publication of the second part, the first volume was a success. *La Pucelle, ou la France délivrée* was considered boring, but in the seventeenth century bourgeoisie, boredom was being accepted as an inevitable consequence of the appreciation of a thirty-thousand-lines poem at the time.¹⁹⁰ The mystery surrounding Joan, coupled with Chapelain’s reputation, and the public’s curiosity, contributed to the poem’s commercial success.¹⁹¹ Many editions in various formats were produced, and the most valuable copies contained

¹⁸⁵ Heimann, “Joan of Arc,” 39.

¹⁸⁶ Jean Chapelain, *La Pucelle, ou la France délivrée, poème héroïque* (Netherland : Janssonius van Waesberge, 1656), 27.

¹⁸⁷ Chapelain, *La Pucelle*, 81.

¹⁸⁸ Françoise Michaud-Fréjaville, “Personne, personnage : Jeanne d’Arc en France au XVIIe siècle,” *Cahiers de Recherches Médiévales* 12 Spé. (2005) : 245.

¹⁸⁹ Michaud-Fréjaville, “Personne,” 245.

¹⁹⁰ Bourque, *Jean Chapelain*, 13.

¹⁹¹ Bourque, *Jean Chapelain*, 13.

illustrations, as grandiose and fictitious as the verses.¹⁹² Some of these served as models for tapestries that still exist in the Musée des Beaux Arts and the Maison de Jeanne d'Arc in Orléans.¹⁹³ Certainly, Chapelain contributed to the popularity of Joan of Arc's legacy through his work over an extended period.

It is noteworthy that *La Pucelle, ou la France délivrée*, a century later, became a source of inspiration for Voltaire, who also wrote a work about Joan. In contrast to Chapelain's admiration for Joan, Voltaire's text tells a scandalous satire on her story. *La Pucelle d'Orléans* remained throughout the nineteenth century a perennial bestseller, albeit an illicit one. Much like Shakespeare, who, for his own agenda, harboured antipathy toward Joan, Voltaire displayed a dismissive attitude toward her. However, Joan's compelling persona captivated him enough to the extent that he wrote an 8500-verse poem. The writing of *La Pucelle d'Orléans*, which contained twenty songs, took thirty years, and was first published in 1762; later in 1773, Voltaire added a twenty-first canto.¹⁹⁴ His motivation came after being challenged by the duke of Richelieu (a relative of the cardinal of Richelieu) to produce a more compelling rendition of the topic than Chapelain had done.¹⁹⁵ Although Voltaire initially wrote this text for the sole purpose of entertaining his friends, he eventually published it in order to respond to defamatory piracy.¹⁹⁶

While Chapelain was inspired by Joan's religious role as the liberator of France and believed in her story, Voltaire saw Joan as belonging to the Dark Ages, when "barbarism, superstition, and ignorance covered the face of the world."¹⁹⁷ Indeed, the eighteenth century was transitioning into a new era of reason, science, and respect for humanity. Subsequently, Voltaire, known as one of the leading philosophers of the Enlightenment, held a deep disdain for all forms of human superstition.¹⁹⁸ His outrage was not aimed at heroism, but at superstition,¹⁹⁹ and Joan happened to be a suitable heroine to convey his message.

¹⁹² Michaud-Fréjaville, "Personne," 244.

¹⁹³ Michaud-Fréjaville, "Personne," 244.

¹⁹⁴ Harman, "La Pucelle," 1.

¹⁹⁵ Harman, "La Pucelle," 1.

¹⁹⁶ Harman, "La Pucelle," 1.

¹⁹⁷ Gies, *Joan of Arc*, 250.

¹⁹⁸ Gies, *Joan of Arc*, 249.

¹⁹⁹ Harman, "La Pucelle," 2.

For Voltaire, God exists, but He belongs to humanity, not to the Church;²⁰⁰ a view that Joan would have shared, as according to one of her assessors, she said that “qu’en certains points, elle n’en croyait ni évêque, ni pape, ni personne; que ce qu’elle avait, elle le tenait de Dieu.”²⁰¹ Joan recognised the lack of trustworthiness in the clergymen assessing her, her faith in God stemmed from the voices she purportedly heard. Subsequently, her alignment with the Enlightenment’s rationalistic mindset stopped there because Voltaire posited that the existence of God is not contingent upon revelations and should be accessible to all.²⁰² While it was Joan’s devoutness to her saints that fuelled her actions, for Voltaire the creed of deism was neither dogmas, rites or revelations.²⁰³

Voltaire’s aim was not only to produce a provoking work that was contrary to Chapelain’s perception of Joan, but also to denounce the bigotry of powerful male members of institutions such as the Catholic Church, the monarchy, and the University of Paris which he believed were inherently corrupt and infamous.²⁰⁴ Later Voltaire stated that should a philosopher have been present on the faculty of theology at the University of Paris during Joan’s trial, she would have been honoured and not condemned to be burned.²⁰⁵ He referred to intolerance, fanaticism and superstition, conveyed and embodied by the Church; subsequently, his words caused indignation among the devout.²⁰⁶ The poem was banned, burned, and widely decried as poisonous, wasteful and extravagant throughout Europe in the eighteenth and nineteenth centuries.²⁰⁷ Despite an official censorship, Voltaires’ work enjoyed widespread popularity for over a century after its first release.²⁰⁸ While it is questionable whether it was Joan’s inherent popularity or the allure of a censored provoking work that contributed to its widespread appeal, it is certain that Joan’s deeds provided ground to demonstrate the Enlightenment’s elevation of spirits.

Appearance in the arts

In the mid-nineteenth century, a notable shift occurred in the depictions of Joan of Arc. She transitioned from being perceived primarily as a solitary figure who had saved France

²⁰⁰ Harman, “La Pucelle,” 2.

²⁰¹ Michelet, 247.

²⁰² Harman, “La Pucelle,” 2.

²⁰³ Harman, “La Pucelle,” 2.

²⁰⁴ Heimann, “Joan of Arc in French Art and Culture,” Chapter 1, np.

²⁰⁵ Gies, *Joan of Arc*, 250.

²⁰⁶ Harman, “La Pucelle,” 2.

²⁰⁷ Heimann, “Joan of Arc in French Art and Culture,” Chapter 1, np.

²⁰⁸ Heimann, “Joan of Arc in French Art and Culture,” Chapter 1, np.

to becoming a source of inspiration for the arts, with her character increasingly seen as emblematic of the common people. Notably, a painting by Ary Scheffer representing the *Entrance of Joan into Orléans* still draws attention in the *Galerie des batailles* in the Château of Versailles.²⁰⁹ Its significance is evidenced by its prominent position at a focal point in the centre of the gallery. In 1830, it replaced the initially planned representation of King Louis Philippe who inaugurated a new political regime, more liberal and constitutional, where the king symbolically renounced to being placed in a central position.²¹⁰ Joan's portrait, as an exemplary figure of French history, had been chosen to have a position in the national museum of Versailles dedicated "to all the glories of France".²¹¹ While Louis Philippe's wished to surround himself with legendary figures, he also aimed to kindle in his visitors a sense of shared history, uniting them through a common heritage.²¹² Accordingly, while symbolising the glory of the country, Joan was considered as an exemplary person.

In addition, Louis Philippe's daughter, Marie d'Orléans, created several statues of Joan of Arc that became particularly popular. One of them, *Jeanne en prière*, was reproduced in several hundred copies.²¹³ It meticulously depicted Joan's costume and hairstyle to an accurate degree that had not been achieved before.²¹⁴ In 1840, King Louis-Philippe commissioned a monumental bronze replica of this statue and offered it, the following year, to the city of Orléans in memory of Joan. The statue still stands in the courtyard of the Hotel Grosloot. Frequently copied, in marble or in bronze, this statue of variable size is a devotional object that can be found throughout France today, in churches and in public squares, affirming her enduring popularity.²¹⁵

The renowned and symbolic statue of *Jeanne en prière*, evoking devoutness appeared in Auguste Vinchon's painting, *Louis-Philippe et la famille royale visitent les Galeries Historiques de Versailles*. In the painting, the scene takes place one evening in 1839 when the sovereigns look at the statue of Joan; the servants hold light reflector lamps above their heads, illuminating the sad faces. The orange light of the lamps, the darkness and the nudity

²⁰⁹ Thomas W. Gaehtgens, "Le Musée Historique de Versailles," in *Les Lieux de mémoire*, Ed. Pierre Nora (Paris : Gallimard, 1984) 153.

²¹⁰ Gaehtgens, "Le Musée Historique de Versailles," 153.

²¹¹ Gaehtgens, "Le Musée Historique de Versailles," 154.

²¹² Gaehtgens, "Le Musée Historique de Versailles," 154.

²¹³ Gaehtgens, "Le Musée Historique de Versailles," 154.

²¹⁴ Heimann, *Joan of Arc*, 46.

²¹⁵ Gaehtgens, "Le Musée Historique de Versailles," 154.

of the vaults of the gallery, contribute to create an atmosphere of contemplation and melancholy due to the premature death of Princess Marie.²¹⁶ *Jeanne en prière* had been one of the king's daughter's last works. Dubois describes the statue as emanating a sense of piety.

Jeanne, figurée debout, l'air humble, la tête penchée, a le visage empreint d'une grande sérénité et d'une grande douceur. Elle serre sur son cœur, les mains jointes, l'épée de sainte Catherine de Fierbois qui prend ainsi des allures de crucifix. Cette posture religieuse est soulignée par les effets de lumière qui nimrent la frêle jeune fille.²¹⁷

Although the sovereigns were paying homage to their deceased daughter, they may have seen in Joan of Arc a representation of sanctity. Marie d'Orléans was clearly touched by the now mystical legend of Joan; her statue depicted Joan as a warrior in armour with sword, but also as a virgin invested with a divine mission. While royal patronage and widespread affection helped to promote Marie d'Orléans's work, the remarkable popularity of her *Jeanne en prière* lay in Joan's posterity suggesting a sentimental piety that was particularly favoured in the mid-1800-s.

National unity

As Joan's popularity was on the ascent, thanks to the public representation designated to her by Louis-Philippe where she was equated with royalty, and to her prominence due to the widespread acclaim of *Jeanne en Prière*; Michelet heralded Joan to new heights as a historical figure whose influence surpassed that of the monarch. In 1841, Michelet extracted the chapter related to Joan of Arc from his major work *Histoire de France* (book V) to make a separate volume entitled *Jeanne d'Arc*. With the publication of this book, a radical transformation of Joan's character took place. Michelet wrote,

Il fallait une autorité, plus que l'autorité royale [...]. Pour réduire ces volontés sauvages, indomptables, il fallait Dieu même. [...] Il fallait la Vierge descendue sur terre, une vierge populaire, jeune, belle, douce, hardie. La guerre avait changé les hommes en bêtes sauvages ; il fallait de ces bêtes refaire des hommes, des chrétiens, des sujets dociles.²¹⁸

²¹⁶ Delphine Dubois, "La statue de Jeanne d'Arc à Versailles", Histoire par l'image, histoire-image.org/etudes/statue-jeanne-arc-versailles.

²¹⁷ Dubois, "La statue de Jeanne d'Arc".

²¹⁸ Michelet, *Histoire*, 189.

Despite being a republican and not a clergyman, Michelet depicted Joan as a divine heroic figure surpassing the king's power, and capable of dominating the battlefield while also possessing the tenderness of a young girl. Michelet's work, posits that Joan's exemplary conduct and her ability to unite those around her were instrumental in shaping the development of France.²¹⁹ Through this, Joan emerged as a powerful commanding figure who instilled a sense of national unity that contributed to the popularisation of her myth.

Akin to Michelet, the artist Jean Fragonard aspired to represent Joan as a national heroine whose pure patriotism and devoutness towards God constituted her core values. Fragonard's painting of *Jeanne sur le bûcher (1822)*, depicted Joan as a young, attractive woman, dressed in white as a symbol of her immaculateness, tied to the pillory, and facing imminent death by burning. She looks up towards an opening of blue sky through the billowing dark clouds of smoke, as if seeking divine intervention. Yet Fragonard does not include any explicit symbols of Christianity or any surrounding crowd, instead, the painting emphasises Joan's extreme loneliness at the stake. It highlights the solitary moment of her death, which stands in stark contrast to her popularity during her lifetime. Fragonard's vision, like Michelet's, stripped Joan of any political undertones or overly compelling ideologies in contrast to the authors, historians or the ecclesiastics who sought to appropriate the national heroine to symbolise their own cause.²²⁰ Their representations suggest an absence of self. Both Fragonard and Michelet saw in Joan a figure who transcended partisan interests where her legacy is rooted in her historical significance as a national heroine. This representation of Joan would have widened her appeal to people from diverse backgrounds, thereby playing a part in the perpetuation of her myth.

The truth about Joan

A pupil of Michelet, Jules Quicherat, further revived the image of Joan of Arc as the daughter of the people when the complete records of the trial as well as chronicles, literary works, letters, public documents and extracts from accounts all related to Joan of Arc were published in his *Procès de condamnation et de réhabilitation de Jeanne d'Arc* in five volumes,

²¹⁹ Gerd Krumeich, "Jeanne d'Arc, héroïne nationale de gauche à droite," Les nuits de France Culture, September 18, 2018, podcast, 14 :00. <https://www.radiofrance.fr/franceculture/podcasts/les-nuits-de-france-culture/lieux-de-memoire-jeanne-d-arc-2-2-que-represente-aujourd-hui-jeanne-d-arc-pour-les-orleanais-1ere-diffusion-13-06-1996-9129300>, 14 :10.

²²⁰ Gerd Krumeich, "Pour une étude comparée de l'iconographie de Jeanne d'Arc," in *La République en représentations*, ed. Maurice Agulhon (Paris : Éditions de la Sorbonne, 2006), 255-263, 8-9. <https://books.openedition.org/psorbonne/59667?lang=fr>.

in the 1840s. Jules Quicherat, professor and then director of the Écoles des Chartes in Paris, dispelled many of the inaccuracies surrounding Joan's trial and execution,²²¹ demonstrating through extensive research that Joan was not the heretic she had been accused of being, but rather a devout Catholic who had been unfairly condemned in an inquisition trial. His book countered the negative representations by writers such as Shakespeare and Voltaire. Through meticulous documentation, including the transcripts of her trial, he instigated a shift in the public's perception of Joan. Subsequently, Joan emerged as an authentic historical figure, and much information about her life was available. Moreover, Quicherat's research shed light on the political motivations behind Joan's trial, revealing that her execution was linked with her role as a military leader and her support for the dauphin, rather than any religious offenses.²²² From that time, the supported evidence of Joan's achievements sparked interest and her profile as an imposing historical figure grew dramatically.

The first unabridged English translation of Quicherat's work, published by W.P. Barrett, became available in 1932 in New York, and historians still refer to his work today, including the last two volumes which collect all the texts known in the middle of the nineteenth century on Joan.²²³ These works changed the view that people had of Joan; she was no longer the mystical legendary heroine of the distant dark ages but a true historical figure.²²⁴ Her astonishing life was documented, and the detailed information despite being mysterious and disturbing led to yet another shift in her popularity as a courageous and pious young woman who had given her life for her country and her faith.

Cultural and political symbolism

The story of Joan of Arc in Quicherat's work was also a source of inspiration for French poet and essayist, Charles Péguy. As a libertarian socialist militant, Péguy found in Joan of Arc a symbol of religious faith and heroism. Péguy's extensive research was partly based on Jules Quicherat's *Procès de condamnation et de réhabilitation de Jeanne d'Arc*.²²⁵ In 1897, his work resulted in the publication of *Le Mystère de la Charité de Jeanne d'Arc*. This lyrical play

²²¹ Gies, *Joan of Arc*, 253.

²²² Gies, *Joan of Arc*, 253

²²³ Colette Beaune, *Jeanne d'Arc* (Perrin, 2004), Le procès en nullité, np.

²²⁴ The story of Joan through Quicherat's work also reached American author, Mark Twain who wrote *Personal Recollections of Joan of Arc* (1896).

²²⁵ Jean Onimus, "Les Sources de la « Jeanne d'Arc » de Péguy," *Revue d'Histoire littéraire de la France*, July- Septembre 1962, 386.

combined elevated monologues on the mystery of God's love for humanity with sober meditations on the themes of sin, suffering and redemption.²²⁶ Joan's narrative articulated Péguy's dissatisfaction with Christian doctrines of eternal damnation, beliefs he felt encouraged bourgeois individualism and societal indifference in the context of human suffering.²²⁷ In Péguy's text, a different perspective on Christian eschatological thinking comes to light. To him, Joan represented an internalised quest for salvation through existential hope.²²⁸ He incited his readers to seek a vulnerable, dependent, hopeful God within the boundaries of our world.²²⁹ The story of Joan of Arc, through Péguy's divergent vision of the Catholic faith and his demand for human solidarity,²³⁰ echoes the national unity posited by Michelet and Fragonard interpretations.

Le Mystère de la Charité de Jeanne d'Arc also served as a source of inspiration for many over time. One notable proponent is Pope Francis, who has recurrently alluded to Péguy's work in recent years.²³¹ In 2006, it was Pope Benedict XVI, who after attending a representation of *Le Mystère de la Charité de Jeanne d'Arc*, praised the play by writing:

The performance of this work for us this evening seems to me especially appropriate. Indeed, in the international context familiar to us today, in the face of the tragic events in the Middle East and situations of suffering caused by violence in many regions of the world, the message transmitted by Charles Péguy in *The Mystery of the Charity of Joan of Arc* remains a most profitable source of reflection.²³²

The pope's message drawn from the interpretation of Péguy's Joan remains relevant as an enriching subject of reflection on the tragic and violent events that take place in the world today. In 2021, Péguy's *Mystery of the charity of Joan of Arc* was reprinted after being identified by scholars as culturally significant and an essential part of the knowledge corpus that constitutes civilisation.²³³

²²⁶ Charles Péguy, *The Mystery of the Charity of Joan of Arc* (Clunymedia, 2021), fourth cover.

<https://clunymedia.com/products/the-mystery-of-the-charity-of-joan-of-arc>

²²⁷ Christopher D. Denny, "Revisiting Dante's Promised End: Eschatological Implications of Péguy's Jeanne d'Arc Mysteries," *The Johns Hopkins University Press*, no.4 (Summer 2013): 534, <https://www.jstor.org/stable/44315045>, 534.

²²⁸ Denny, "Revisiting Dante's Promised End," 534.

²²⁹ Denny, "Revisiting Dante's Promised End," 558.

²³⁰ Denny, "Revisiting Dante's Promised End," 542.

²³¹ Benjamin Ivry, "Charles Péguy : a poet trapped between heaven and earth," *Catholic Herald* (March 2020).

²³² His Holiness Benedict XVI, "Performance of Charles Péguy: *The Mystery of the Charity of Joan of Arc*" *Libreria Editrice Vaticana* (August 2006).

²³³ Péguy, *The Mystery*, fourth cover.

Through his writing, Péguy recommended that “a socialist utopia was to be founded on earth,”²³⁴ rather than hoping for its realisation in heaven. At the time, the French republic was divided by the Dreyfus affair. While Joan had held great appeal for socialists, as one the most powerful symbols available to propagandists, she underwent a transformation. She evolved into a socio-political symbol of patriotism for the French Republicans as well as a rallying point for anti-Semites. In this context, Péguy endeavoured to mobilise his fellow socialists to support the cause of establishing Alfred Dreyfus’ innocence.

From 1894 till 1906, the Dreyfus Affair captured the attention of the public and led to a deep divide in France. The case was seen as having implications that went far beyond the guilt or innocence of Alfred Dreyfus. Instead, it served to amplify pre-existing xenophobic and anti-Semitic sentiments that were then prevalent.²³⁵ Alfred Dreyfus, a Jewish captain in the military, was accused of selling military secrets, and convicted of treason; he was sentenced to life imprisonment in December 1894. However, he was later found to be innocent, and the evidence against him to have been falsified as part of an anti-Semitic campaign. His verdict and sentence were welcomed by both a substantial part of the population, and the French press, that were largely influenced by the virulently anti-Semitic faction.

The book *La France Juive*, written and published in 1886 by Edouard Drumont, unleashed a torrent of anti-Semitic sentiment.²³⁶ Drumont, wrote that, “La France pouvait avoir un réveil comme elle en eut un avec Jeanne d’Arc, se relever brusquement au moment d’expirer, rejeter violemment les traîtres qui l’avaient fait rouler si bas, appeler le Roi à son secours et gagner une suprême bataille.”²³⁷ Drumont assimilated the Freemasons, the Jews, and the Protestants to the English invaders at the time of Joan of Arc, and held them responsible for France’s apparent decline. Since they were considered to be traitors by far-right politicians such as himself, Drumont wanted them driven out of the Republic of France.²³⁸ Referring to Joan of Arc as a “pure héroïne, le symbole du relèvement national,”²³⁹ he believed that she had, against all odds, successfully participated to the expulsion of the English out of France. This established her as an exemplary leader who had safeguarded the

²³⁴ Denny, “Revisiting Dante’s Promised End,” 536.

²³⁵ Krumeich, “Jeanne d’Arc,” podcast.

²³⁶ Jennifer Kilgore, “Joan of Arc as Propaganda Motif from the Dreyfus Affair to the Second World War,” *Revue LISA/LISA e-journal*, Vol. VI – n°1 (2008). <https://journals.openedition.org/lisa/519?lang=en>

²³⁷ Edouard Drumont, *La France Juive* (Paris V. Palme, 1890), 181. Archive.org.

²³⁸ Drumont, *La France Juive*, 317.

²³⁹ Drumont, *La France Juive*, 317.

nation's "purity", a quality that the xenophobic journalist was seeking. Subsequently, the ideology was supported by a significant part of the population and made Joan the symbol of anti-Semitism.

The newspaper *La Libre Parole*, founded and edited by Drumont, played a significant role in using the Dreyfus Affair to perpetuate the stereotype of disloyalty among French Jews.²⁴⁰ Drumont saw Joan as being of the "pure race" that was to the credit and benefit of France and he suggested her superiority over those of Semitic origin. On May 30, 1894, in *La Libre Parole*, with a deep-seated anti-Semitic ideology, he characterised Joan as an "aryenne baptisée".²⁴¹ He not only saw in Joan her determination to drive outsiders out of France, but also, adding to her benefit, the privilege of being perceived as divinely blessed. It is a rather ironic coincidence that Dreyfus' oppressors found solace in gathering around Joan's statue. To Dreyfus, Joan had been, much like himself, a victim of political machinery that showed no regards for individual rights.²⁴² Dreyfus had named his daughter Jeanne, perhaps in memory of Joan.²⁴³ Despite their different backgrounds, both Joan and Dreyfus shared a common belief in the necessity of upholding infallible justice and the recognition that authorities can make mistakes.²⁴⁴ Joan, renowned for her bravery and heroism during her lifetime, served as an archetype of the victim of personal oppression, just like Dreyfus. While being disputed and appropriated by opposing socio-political factions in the late 1800s and early 1900s, Joan's life and experiences continued to be harnessed as a symbol of hope and inspiration for individuals who strived to overcome the constraints of unjust systems and circumstances.

Sainthood

It is notable that many of those who spent time with Joan of Arc, or wrote about her, have consistently conveyed a sense of holiness about her, regardless of their biases or political learnings. This perception of Joan began to take hold right from the time when she departed from Vaucouleurs accompanied by the young men who felt "inflamed by her divine love."²⁴⁵ Even on the English side during her execution, one of Henry VI's secretaries exclaimed, "We

²⁴⁰ Kilgore, "Joan of Arc as Propaganda," 3.

²⁴¹ Kilgore, "Joan of Arc as Propaganda," 3.

²⁴² Kilgore, "Joan of Arc as Propaganda," 10.

²⁴³ Kilgore, "Joan of Arc as Propaganda," 9.

²⁴⁴ Jussem-Wilson, "L'Affaire," 403.

²⁴⁵ Wallon, *Jeanne d'Arc*, Volume 1, 105.

are all lost, for we have burnt a saint!”.²⁴⁶ This enduring recognition of Joan’s sanctity led to her canonisation, nearly 500 years after her death.²⁴⁷ Following the yearly celebrations in memory of Joan of Arc in Orléans in 1869, Bishop Dupanloup gathered the attending bishops and urged them to sign an address to Leo XIII, the reigning Sovereign Pontiff in Rome at the time, requesting the honours of canonisation for Joan.²⁴⁸ Almost twenty years later, in 1890, Rome accepted this request, declaring Joan as venerable. The next step towards canonisation was beatification, which was officially proclaimed on April 18, 1909. Rome waited until after the First World War, and on May 16, 1920; Pope Benedict XV officiated at Saint Peter's Basilica in Rome to finally canonise Joan of Arc, declaring her the patron saint of France. This was a significant event for those who had supported her cause, as it elevated Joan to sainthood, and meant that martyrs, captives, and prisoners could all look to her as their patron saint. This ceremony, which occurred five centuries after her death, represented Joan’s apotheosis.

Les fêtes Jeanne d’Arc

Prior to the formal recognition of her sainthood, *Les fêtes Jeanne d’Arc* commemorated Joan’s enduring legacy by celebrating her bravery, patriotism, as well as her exemplary religious devotion. The *Fêtes de Jeanne d’Arc* emerged on May 8, 1429, following the lifting of the siege in Orléans, when a spontaneous thanksgiving procession took place between the cathedral and the Tourelles.²⁴⁹ The following year, the municipality, the clergy, and the count of Dunois, acting on behalf of the duke of Orléans organised a commemorative procession to honour Joan’s deeds.²⁵⁰ This procession was repeated in subsequent years, and became one of the earliest commemorative festivals of the Middle Ages during which a play accompanied by music and props re-enacted the events.²⁵¹ It culminated with the symbolic entry in Orléans of Joan of Arc that had brought a remarkable sense of relief to the inhabitants.²⁵² This tradition endured until 1855 when a new ceremony was introduced. It involved the delivery of the standard followed by a historical procession also depicting Joan's entry into the city.²⁵³ The French Revolution briefly interrupted these celebrations, but they

²⁴⁶ Krumeich, “Jeanne d’Arc,” podcast, 6:00.

²⁴⁷ Gies, *Joan of Arc*, 225.

²⁴⁸ Laurent, *Saint Jeanne d’Arc*, 177.

²⁴⁹ Bouzy et al., “*Les fêtes de Jeanne*”, 22.

²⁵⁰ Beaune, *Naissance de la nation*, 180.

²⁵¹ Bouzy et al., “*Les fêtes de Jeanne*”, 22.

²⁵² Beaune, *Naissance de la nation*, 180.

²⁵³ Beaune, *Naissance de la nation*, 180-1.

were reinstated in 1803 by the First Consul Bonaparte, responding to the wishes of the inhabitants of Orléans.²⁵⁴ Even during the tumultuous period of the Second World War, the festivities continued, albeit in a more subdued manner. In 1945, during the annual procession, the cathedral's bells rang to announce the surrender of the German army and the liberation of France on 8 May, a fortuitous date that left a profound impact on the collective consciousness, as it was the anniversary of Joan's entry into the city.²⁵⁵ Despite the passage of six centuries since the inception of these celebrations that are still popular today. Two main elements have persisted: the religious observance associated with Joan's devotion, and the secular aspect that highlights her historical and cultural importance for France.²⁵⁶

The city of Orléans has preserved the myth of Joan of Arc through its annual celebrations which foster cohesion among diversity by bringing together civil institutions, religious authorities and military forces.²⁵⁷ A notable aspect of these celebrations is the customary invitation extended to the President of the Republic, regardless of his political affiliation, emphasising the importance of collective representation and transcending partisan boundaries.²⁵⁸ Despite a de facto separation between the civil institutions and religious authorities that was established in the wake of the French Revolution, a point is made of honouring a historical Joan of Arc who delivered the city. Moreover, the commemorative events associated with Joan of Arc's legacy have gained international recognition. They are now included on the Intangible cultural heritage list and considered by UNESCO as an integral part of French cultural heritage.²⁵⁹ This recognition in prestigious international registers is a development that would have been unimaginable to the young girl of Domrémy. It underscores the enduring importance of these festivities in upholding the myth and legacy of Joan of Arc as a symbol of unity.

Joan in the world

Joan of Arc's remembrance has also radiated into foreign countries. Joan was a heroine of Indira Gandhi, as her father, Jawaharlal Nehru, reminded her in the letters that formed his book, *Glimpses of World History*. In his view, Joan instilled a beginning of national

²⁵⁴ Bouzy et al., "Les fêtes de Jeanne", 22.

²⁵⁵ Bouzy et al., "Les fêtes de Jeanne", 23.

²⁵⁶ Bouzy et al., "Les fêtes de Jeanne", 22.

²⁵⁷ Bouzy et al., "Les fêtes de Jeanne", 7.

²⁵⁸ Bouzy et al., "Les fêtes de Jeanne", 7.

²⁵⁹ Bouzy et al., "Les fêtes de Jeanne".

identity in France as she aimed to save the whole country at a time when people were more familiar with feudalism better than nationalism.²⁶⁰ Furthermore, according to Nora Heimann, during the period spanning from the Gilded Age (1880-1914) to World War I, Joan of Arc captivated a diverse spectrum of Americans. A plethora of original art pieces from that era, along with plaster casts, reductions, and replicas of prominent French sculptures and monuments featuring the Maid of Orléans found a place in American schools, museums, and parks.²⁶¹ Later, as mass media and popular entertainment expanded in the United States, Joan's patriotic image became even more potent among an audience highly receptive to such influences.²⁶² Many artists have used Joan as a source of inspiration in their work to entertain their audience. From 1800 in Germany, Joan takes on the character of an idealist with blood on her hands in Schiller's popular play *Die Jungfrau von Orléans*. In 1845, her story inspired Verdi to produce the Italian version of *Giovanna d'Arco*. Similarly, in Russia in 1880, Tchaikovsky loosely based his opera titled *Maid of Orléans* on Schiller's play. In 1917, Joan of Arc became the protagonist and titular character of the world's first feature film, directed by Cécil B. DeMille. Since then, Joan's narrative has been extensively portrayed in approximately fifty films across various national cinemas, including French, American, Italian and German.²⁶³ These films collectively celebrate Joan of Arc as a distinctive and adaptable symbol of female heroism, throughout different historical periods and geographical locations, thus perpetrating her enduring myth.

²⁶⁰ Jawaharlal Nehru, *Glimpses of World History* (New York: Asia Publishing House, 1934), 243. <https://archive.org>.

²⁶¹ Laura Coyle, "A Universal patriot: Joan of Arc in America During the Gilded Age and the great War," in *Joan of Arc: her image in France and America* (Washington DC, Antique collectors' Club Ltd, 2006), 53. <https://archive.org>.

²⁶² Coyle, "A universal patriot", 73.

²⁶³ Mairie d'Orléans, "Jeanne d'Arc Laissez-vous conter Jeanne d'Arc,"(2014).

Conclusion

If there were a recipe to create a myth, Joan of Arc would have been the embodiment of all its ingredients at a fortuitous moment in history. Her apparition occurred at a time when religion played a dominant role in everyday life, and when divine intervention seemed the only way to improve France's fortunes. Moreover, Joan of Arc was viewed as an exalted warrior who drove the enemy out of France, and embodied the archetype of the young, rebellious heroine-martyr. Throughout history, the depiction of Joan of Arc has taken shape and evolved in accordance with debates and interests of each respective era. Besides, the absence of contemporary reproduction, depicting her physical appearance, provided a blank canvas upon which a variety of characteristics could be appropriated to serve numerous purposes. Consequently, various authorities saw in her their potential icon to champion their causes. For instance, her desire to expel the English out of France has been analogously applied by nationalist politicians to remove foreigners out of their own country. Additionally, her devout faith has inspired religious groups while her leadership skills have inspired military figures. Integrated into a national memory with a complex construction, the figure of the sacrificed warrior has lent itself well to various ideals, even if it has meant undergoing numerous distortions along the way. Ignorance, superstition, heroism, and patriotism are all themes that are frequently intertwined and confounded in the myth of Joan of Arc. Despite the allegations of heresy, her conviction, her untimely demise, and historical as well as literary vilifications endured over the passage of time, Joan of Arc has remained a source of fascination, inspiring numerous individuals to clear her name and to glorify her status, culminating with her canonisation. Remarkably, as her myth endures, her legacy is still recognised in contemporary times.

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Appendices

Map of France in 1429

Les « Trois France » en 1429 : zones d'influences respectives de la double monarchie franco-anglaise, du royaume de Bourges et du duché de Bourgogne avant l'intervention de Jeanne d'Arc. Courtesy of Wikimedia Commons.

https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:La_France_en_1429.svg.

Jeanne sur le bûcher

Jeanne sur le bûcher, huile sur toile d'Alexandre-Évariste Fragonard, 1822, Musée des Beaux-Arts de Rouen. Courtesy of Wikipedia.